

TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Translation studies is the science of translation as a process and as a text, which studies the problems of translation, the main stages of its formation and development, its theoretical foundations - general and specific, the methodology and technique of the translation process, the formation of translation skills and abilities to transmit information from one language to another in oral and written form. Thus, the main specificity of translation studies lies in the study of speech and language activity in a bilingual situation, when the process of communication (oral and / or written) is carried out by means of two languages.

In accordance with the above-mentioned problems of the science of translation, the following main sections are distinguished in it.

1. The history of translation, which examines the place, role and evolution of translation in connection with the development of human society, its material and spiritual culture, political and economic ties, and also studies the process of formation and development of translation thought and national translation traditions based on the analysis of relevant sources - historical monuments of translation and their authors.
2. General translation theory, which deals with problems that are common to all types of translation, regardless of the specific varieties of the latter (genres, forms, types) and the features of the language material. Therefore, it is sometimes said that the subject of the general theory of translation is TRANSLATION UNIVERSALS (Latin: Universalis - universal). This term is taken from linguistics, where universals are properties inherent in all languages.
3. Specific translation theories, the subject of which are types of translation and genre features of the translated material (fiction and special texts), various forms and types of translation (both oral and written), features of translation into different languages and translation using a computer (machine translation and machine translation).
4. Translation methodology, the purpose of which is to develop the appropriate skills and abilities, i.e. teaching the TECHNIQUE of translation based on the knowledge obtained by general and specific translation theories.
5. Translation criticism is a separate area, which deals with the analysis of the translated text and the establishment of the degree of its adequacy to the original text from linguistic, literary-aesthetic and other points of view. This area

of translation studies is closely connected with the theory of literary translation, since it deals primarily with translated works related to fiction in the broad sense of the word.

Translation as a type of spiritual activity of man dates back to ancient times. It has always played a significant role in the history of the culture of individual nations and world culture as a whole. In our time - since the middle of the 20th century (after the Second World War) - translation activity in all its varieties has acquired an unprecedented scope due to the ever-increasing intensity of international contacts.

The word "translation" is one of the well-known and generally understood, but it, as a designation of a special type of human activity and its result, requires clarification and terminological definition.

The process of translation (and its result) takes place in a bilingual situation, when two languages are involved in the process of communication, i.e. an interlingual situation, then translation can also be defined as a process of interlingual transformation or transformation of an oral or written text presented in one language into a text (oral or written) in another language. If language is a naturally existing communicative system of society, and speech is the functioning of language in the process of communication for the transfer of information, then translation is the transfer of information contained in a given work of speech by means of another language.

Carrying out communicative activity in a bilingual situation, the translator simultaneously codes and decodes the information processed by him in the codes of two different sign systems. Therefore, the process of translation can be considered a complex type of psycholinguistic activity in a bilingual situation.

We considered the process of translation above as an act of speech-language communication occurring in a bilingual situation, i.e. as interlingual translation. However, in the process of everyday communication in various situations and areas of communication, the transfer of information is carried out in a monolingual situation, i.e. in the same language. In all types of monolingual situations, intralingual translation is carried out all the time, constantly.

Intralingual translation is the recoding of a text from one functional style, from one genre to another, retelling in the same language, presentation, adaptation of a text, etc.

Both intralingual and intersemiotic translations, being special phenomena, in a number of moments come into contact with interlingual translation and allow a better understanding of the patterns inherent in the latter.

Communication between people takes place within the framework of various social situations of communication, which are created by people entering into an act of communication. Therefore, teaching communication within various social situations is associated with learning to analyze and understand the motives of people's actions, taking into account the place of speech activity in human life in general and the factors that have the most direct influence on it. This problem should be considered not only as one of the forms of analysis and understanding of human actions, but also as one of the forms of familiarization with the norms of communication of potential communicants.

It was also important that, having begun to study translation, linguists quickly discovered that not only linguistics can make a great contribution to the theory of translation, but translation can also give much to linguistics itself. Translations turned out to be a valuable source of information about the languages involved in the translation process. In the course of translation activity, which is carried out on such a large scale in the modern world, a kind of linguistic experiment in the communicative equalization of statements and texts in two languages takes place. In this case, similarities and differences in the use of units and structures of each of these languages to express the same functions and describe the same situations are discovered. Thanks to this, it is possible to discover some features of the structure and functioning of the language that escaped attention when using other research methods.

An additional stimulus for the development of linguistic translation theory were attempts to create various machine translation systems. The advent of high-speed computers gave rise to hopes that the functions of a translator would be performed much more quickly and cheaply by an increasingly sophisticated computer. Computers were successfully used to decode encrypted messages, and translation could be thought of as decoding a text in the target language encrypted using the original language. The first attempts at machine translation gave unsatisfactory results, but there were hopes that new generations of computers with larger memory capacities would cope with this task more successfully. However, it soon became clear that the main problems with machine translation were not related to the insufficient memory of the computer, but to the inability to create a program that would allow the machine to overcome numerous translation difficulties as successfully as a person does. And then it turned out that no one could explain how a person translates, since this type of human activity remained insufficiently studied. Therefore, many

linguists who were studying machine translation issues switched their attention to studying “human” translation, trying to find ways to overcome difficulties there.

At present, modern machine translation programs cannot provide high-quality translation of texts of any complexity and, naturally, do not claim to completely replace a human translator. Nevertheless, machine translation is successfully used in three main cases. Firstly, the program is created to translate highly specialized texts, standard in form, with a limited composition of vocabulary and grammar. Secondly, the machine makes it possible to quickly obtain a large volume of low-quality translations, which allow us to judge the general content of the originals and decide what in them is advisable to give to the translator for more accurate reproduction. Thirdly, an editor is included in the work, who either prepares the text for translation (pre-editing), eliminating or clarifying places that are difficult for the machine, or edits the already translated text (post-editing), eliminating errors and inaccuracies.

The subjective factor also played a certain role. Translation faculties and departments were created mainly at universities and institutes of foreign languages, and the training of future translators was carried out by teachers of foreign languages, philologists and linguists. It was they who, first of all, realized the need for a theoretical understanding of translation activities and tried to solve this problem using the methods of their science.

An important place in translation studies is occupied by the method of linguistic modeling: the construction of theoretical models of the translation process. Since this process is carried out through a series of mental operations in the translator's head, it is inaccessible to direct observation and is a kind of "black box". A linguistic model of the translation process presents it as a series of successive transformations of the original text into the translation text, with the help of which the desired result can theoretically be achieved. Although any translation model is hypothetical in nature, since there is no direct evidence that the translator acts exactly as follows from this model, the coincidence of the translation result with that predicted by the model shows that it has a certain explanatory power. In modern translation studies, there are several translation models, which suggests the possibility of carrying out the translation process in different ways.

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